

Using modern interactive technology during learning English

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ABSTRACT.

Nowadays, modern technologies and tools have begun to be actively used in education system, which students to gain knowledge in the process of interacting with each other. One of the most popular modern technologies is a “quest”. This article presents the development of a quest for not only English but also other foreign languages.

Key words: modern technology methods, methods, methodology, quest technology, quests

In interactive education, there are so many new teaching methods. The main function of the methods is the transfer and organization of assimilation of knowledge by students. Teachers and methodologists are looking for different ways to make the learning process easier and more interesting. It is important to make the lessons interesting and creative, because the result of learning and understanding the content of the lesson depends on the presentation of the material. “Education is the key to unlocking the world. It is the passport to freedom “. These words belong to Oprah Winfrey. Language implies communication, interaction between people. For the development of communication skills, it is important to include exercises containing the interaction and communication of students. Moreover, foreign language teachers focus on interactive teaching methods.

In modern teacher education, as well as in vocational education in general, integrative trends of internationalization, globalization, Europeanization, professional development education are manifested. It is known that modern higher pedagogical education involves the study by students of a large number of different academic disciplines, each of which has its own sign system of information, due to the corresponding basic science. Considering that the student age is sensitive enough not only to receive new information, but also to develop the spiritual, intellectual, bodily functions of the body. In order to achieve the practical goal of teaching English, the final practical goal of teaching English in the general school course is listening and reading, that is, getting information by listening and reading in a foreign language. The intermediate practical goal is interpreted differently: in class I, listening comprehension and speaking are practical goals; in II-IV classes, listening comprehension and speaking is a practical goal, a means of repeating and strengthening language material learned in reading and writing oral speech; Among the 31 types of speech activity in grades V – VI, listening comprehension, speaking and reading are intermediate practical goals, writing is a practical tool; In grades VII – IX, listening comprehension and reading are practical goals, speaking and writing

are tools. It is known that any goal arises out of necessity. Educational goals are determined based on analytical data about objective and subjective needs. When determining educational goals, it is necessary to give priority to the communicative needs of students.

In addition, the combination of software and digital devices allows teachers to provide personalized content. For example, the most beneficial aspect of using technology in the classroom is that it improves students' flexibility in the learning process. This is very important because a student who cannot adopt to the lesson will not fully understand it. Secondly, it enriches the cooperation of students with each other.

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